

**DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' PERFORMING AND
MUSICAL ABILITIES THROUGH INSTRUMENTS**

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the pedagogical importance of using musical instruments in music lessons in secondary schools. The issues of developing students' performing skills, musical hearing, rhythm and musical thinking through children's musical instruments are analyzed. Also, ways of forming musical culture and aesthetic taste in students through the use of national and world musical instruments are shown.

One of the main tasks of music science in the modern education system is to develop students' musical abilities, educate them in the spirit of national and universal culture. The state program for the implementation of the new development strategy of Uzbekistan for the period of 2022-2026 in the "Year of honoring human

dignity and active neighborhood" on additional measures for the further development of the sphere of culture and art.[1] Musical instruments play a special role in this process. Playing music through musical instruments helps students to understand music more deeply, feel its content, and increase their creative activity.

The use of children's musical instruments in music lessons develops not only students' musical knowledge, but also personal qualities such as teamwork, concentration, and discipline. Therefore, this article will widely cover the pedagogical possibilities of musical instruments in music lessons. Music, with its unique nature, has the power to greatly influence the spiritual world of young people.[2]

Musical instruments are an integral part of the art of music, through which the artistic expression of melody and tone is manifested. In music education, musical instruments are an important tool for developing musical hearing, rhythm, and performance skills in students. Especially simple musical instruments intended for children (circle, spoon, drum, metallophone, etc.) are of great pedagogical importance at the initial stage. At the same time, individual work, differentiated teaching, the application of which in the process of school education is somewhat difficult, allows you to provide theoretical and practical knowledge that is not taken into account in the programs of the subject "Musical Culture", integrates and enriches the educational mechanism. Specialized music schools differ from general secondary schools in the relatively large amount of knowledge that must be mastered. In addition, it is necessary to check the octave of some frets in each string.[3]

In the process of playing the instrument, students practically master the tempo, dynamics and rhythmic structure of music. This serves to increase musical literacy.

National musical instruments - dutor, tanbur, rubab, doira, gijjak and nay - form respect and interest in national musical culture in students. The principles that form the worldview of the choral culture are especially important today, when universal spiritual values are being revived.[4] The melodies and songs performed by these instruments develop the aesthetic taste of students and educate them in the spirit of national values.

The use of national musical instruments in music lessons enriches the historical and cultural knowledge of students and allows them to integrate music with other subjects.

In order to effectively organize instrumental performance in music lessons, the music teacher must take into account the age and individual characteristics of students. It is advisable that the lessons begin with simple rhythmic exercises and gradually move on to more complex performance elements. The teacher also examines each child's musical ability.[5]

The following methods are considered effective in organizing instrumental performance:

- demonstration and practical exercises;
- collective and group performance;
- listening and repetition method;
- development of performance through musical games.

Music and singing activities have been of special importance in compositional creativity since ancient times.[6] In conclusion, the use of musical instruments in music lessons is of important pedagogical importance in developing students' musical and performance abilities. Through instrumental performance, students develop a sense of music, creative thinking and aesthetic taste. In particular, the use of national musical instruments enriches the spiritual world of students and educates them in the spirit of national culture.

Therefore, enriching music lessons with musical instruments in general secondary schools is one of the important tasks of modern music education.

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